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The Use of Metacognition to Develop Self-Regulated Learning Skills in Students of a Computer Programming Course

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ABSTRACT

In 2013, the Twente Educational Model (TOM) was introduced in the Bachelor programme of the University of Twente, aiming at increasing the motivation and improving the learning results of the students. TOM prescribed that the programmes should have 'integrated thematic modules' of 15EC. In one of these modules, software design and programming are offered to first-year 'Computer Science' (CS) and 'Business Information Technology' (BIT) students. Since most CS students had prior knowledge and experience in programming and/or were more intrinsically motivated to learn programming than BIT students, the BIT students performed generally much poorer than CS students. This paper discusses our efforts to improve the performance of BIT students by helping them become independent learners. To achieve this, we conceived a new pedagogical design to induce metacognition cycles integrated with a mentoring scheme. To help students self-assess themselves and provide structure to the mentoring scheme, we offered the students a study plan, which is a structured view of the syllabus. We broke the learning objectives down into smaller topics, which are units to be learned in one day, and we assigned three student-friendly rubrics to each topic (entry, intermediate, and target) allowing the students to grade their own proficiency level. Every two weeks, students had to self-assess their proficiency in the topics and discuss it with their assigned mentor. This paper shows that these actions have created an awareness of the learning process and consequently improved the students' motivation and end results.

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1 INTRODUCTION

In 2013, the Twente Educational Model (TOM) was introduced in the Bachelor programme of the University of Twente, aiming at increasing the motivation and improving the learning results of the students. In TOM, the curriculum of each programme is composed of so called *integrated thematic modules* of 15EC each, where some of these modules are shared amongst programmes for the sake of efficiency. One of these modules is the first year introduction to software design and implementation (programming), which was until recently shared between the Computer Science (CS) and Business Information Technology (BIT) students.

In this module, we noticed that the students with prior programming knowledge and skills in general performed better in the programming parts of the module than students without this prior knowledge, since the programming learning objectives of the module were quite ambitious. Initially, this difference in programming knowledge and skills was due to the lack of a standardised Computer Science / Information technology high school curriculum in the country of this university, so the programming literacy of the students was determined by how each school approached the subject and/or the hobbies pursued by these students. After 2016, the CS and BIT programmes started to also accept international students, so this difference in knowledge and skills became even more stringent.

Although the differentiating factor was their knowledge and skills, we noticed that BIT students in general performed much worse than CS students in the programming activities in terms of the passing rate (38% passed, compared to 55% of the CS students, in the 2019-2020 academic year). This can be justified by the lower intrinsic motivation of the BIT students, since if they were more motivated to study programming they would have selected the CS programme. This means that in order to solve this problem we need to do something about their motivation, by making programming more appealing and interesting for them. Due to a huge increase in the students inflow, in 2020 the module has been split into two, a BIT and a CS version, and we got an excellent opportunity to apply novel education approaches to solve this problem.

This paper discusses our efforts to improve the performance of the BIT in the programming activities of their introductory module in software design and programming. We achieved this by introducing a new pedagogical design to induce Metacognition cycles integrated with a mentoring scheme. In this effort, we aimed at improving the learning process without decreasing the ambition of the programming learning goals, by aiming at increasing retention and consequently obtaining a higher passing rate.

This paper is structured as follows: Section 2 introduces the methodology used in our work. Section 3 discusses the theoretical constructs that informed the design decisions taken on the intervention. Section 4 presents details of the intervention and their relation with the theoretical constructs of our theoretical framework. The intervention took place in the 2nd quarter of the academic year 2020-2021 and the results are discussed in the Section 5. Finally, Section 6 gives our conclusions and recommendations for future work.

2 METHODOLOGY

This article is part of a long-term Action Research (AR) project that aims to improve the performance of students of the 'Bachelors Information Technology' (B-BIT) Programme in the various courses of computer programming offered in the programme. In the AR project we define the community that will benefit from this research (students, faculty, and other roles related to the BIT Programme), their goals to be pursued following the needs and desires of this community and, in a practical way, we provide a longitudinal view of the results of this research. We follow the guidelines and procedure to perform the AR cycles according to [1] and [2].

In this project, we perform interventions either on the Pedagogical Design or on the Technological Support offered. We act like the 'designers' defined in [3]: *anyone who devises courses of action aimed at changing existing situations into preferred ones* (p.55). We design these interventions to last three months (a quarter), which is the duration of each course provided during an academic year. Therefore, these interventions contribute to a cross-sectional view of this research at a certain point in time. Because the interventions are based on artifacts (new pedagogical processes or new software), the ways we typically act to *change existing situations into preferred ones*, Design-Science Research (DSR) was chosen as a suitable method for the cross-sectional investigations of this research project, while the AR deals with the long-term goals of the community and the analysis of longitudinal data.

The cross-sectional investigation reported in this article is related to the Module Software Development (2nd quarter, 1st year, B-BIT). As observed in [4], DSR goes beyond merely designing and testing particular interventions. *The interventions must embody specific theoretical claims about the teaching and learning*. More than testing the artifact, the analysis of the intervention must feedback the theoretical body that informed the design of the intervention in the first place [5]. Was the artifact correctly designed, i.e. does it embody the theoretical claims it supports investigating? What are the updates, additions, corroborations, and revisions, that the analysis of the intervention done with the said artifact offers to the theoretical body that informed it beforehand?

The research problem (RP) indicated by the community to which this Action Research project was designed is (RP1) *the low performance of BIT students in the various programming courses offered in the Programme*. While we expect to make several interventions in the next years aiming at improving the performance of our students, we chose to start by addressing this research problem by helping students becoming more 'independent-learners'. From the faculty point of view, we expect students to progressively learn more topics on their own.

In order to solve the research problem, we aimed at answering two research questions that help us better understand the problem and how to address it: (RQ1) *How do students use and perceive the periodical review of their proficiency in the topics taught in the course?* This question aims at understanding whether the approach is well-received by students and also investigate any possible phenomenon related to it, like *do students correctly self-assess their level of proficiency? Do they overestimate or underestimate their levels of proficiency? How does it compare to the grades they obtained?* (RQ2) *How did students perform this year in comparison with previous editions?* The analysis of the intervention counts on data collected from the course itself, like test and project grades, reports and essays submitted by students, submissions of weekly exercises together with the feedback and correction. We also consider qualitative data gathered from participants like interviews and surveys done with students, mentors and teachers.

3 THEORETICAL FOUNDATION

Learning computer programming is complex and has been approached in several ways by researchers in computer programming education. In particular Cognitive Load Theory (CLT) has been used to improve the design of instructional material [6][7][8], especially for introductory courses [9][10][11], while Self-Regulated Learning (SRL) and Metacognition theories have approached the monitoring of the learning process as a way to support it [12][13][14]. Cognitive Load Theory (CLT) explains that problem solving tasks (like computer programming) have a way higher cognitive load [15], and learning them depends on previous experience and how developed are their metacognition skills, which are necessary to regulate learning processes that are often lengthy and complex. [16][17].

Figure 1: The three-layered model of Self-Regulated Learning (adapted from [18]).

Figure 1 shows the SRL model of Boekaerts [18], which organizes the 'Regulation of the Learning Process' as an intermediary layer. Metacognition has been used to help regulate the learning process, while also offering benefits to the innermost layer by supporting cognitive strategies [16].

3.1 SRL and Metacognition

Research on SRL and Metacognition has provided evidence that monitoring the cognitive process, which happens in the metacognition cycles, positively affects cognitive processes [13] [19]. The same effect is sought with the improvement of instructional material following advice from CLT. However, while CLT aims at reducing the cognitive load or making it easier to manage, Metacognition focuses on paving the road to learn and monitoring the learning progress. In that sense, it is worth highlight the work of Glogger-Frey *et al.* [20], in which they present findings that the self-regulated group presented better results than the group that received direct instruction - after some practice - although the guidance provided to the instructed group led to lower extraneous load. This is often sought in CLT research as a way to improve the quality of the instructional design. The Metacognition approach requires that the students have enough practice time for their results to surpass those that received a well-designed direct instruction. Well-designed instructions bring faster results and tangible benefits, like the reduction of the extraneous load. The downside of only offering well-designed instructions in the computer science field is that this field requires professionals to learn and adapt quickly to new technologies. Well-designed instructions are often not present to support this need for constant learning and adaptation. However, as pointed out by Kunh and Dean [21], *Metacognition is what enables a student who has been taught a particular strategy in a particular problem context to retrieve and deploy that strategy in a similar but new context.* The schema transfer-ability benefits of Metacognition makes it suitable for equipping the students to learn not only the topic at hand but also to improve their performance in future studying endeavors.

Havenga *et al.* [13] argue that a possible reason for the lower performance of students in computer programming may be that 'students mainly focus on the *product* of programming, namely on computer programs, rather than on the *process* of programming' (p.3). Using Metacognition to improve programming learning seems to be convenient because programming consists of formalizing the process used to solve a problem [19](p.2) [12][14].

3.2 Metacognition Cycles

The model proposed by Flavell in [22] is described as an interplay among our metacognitive knowledge, metacognitive experiences, goals or tasks, and actions or strategies. The metacognitive knowledge can relate to three domains: Person, Task, and Strategy. Knowledge on the Person domain refers to knowing the one's weaknesses and strengths (knowledge about the self or the other), while the knowledge on the Task is regarded to the characteristics of the learning effort (topics that are easier, topics that requires practice, etc.), and the knowledge about the Strategy relates to how to tackle a certain learning endeavor. One example of the three variables at interplay can be illustrated as "you believe that you (unlike your brother) should use strategy A (rather than strategy B) in task X (as contrasted with task Y)" [22](p.6)

4 INTERVENTION

To tackle the low-performance problem of the B-BIT students, we decided to invest in pedagogical designs that emancipate students, helping them be more independent learners, hence the choice for SRL and Metacognition. To support the development of SRL skills in our students, we planned a structured intervention with the following points:

- a. Support students' reflection with a structured syllabus (*Personal Learning Records*).
- b. Create a mentoring system to support students to reflect/prospect.
- c. Create checkpoint meetings one-on-one (mentor/mentee) based on the self-assessment.

The three aforementioned measures are tightly connected to the establishment of a 'culture of reflection.' While students receive the task to self-assess their knowledge every other week (item a), this self-assessment serves as a conversation starter for the bi-weekly meeting among mentors and mentees (item c), also mandatory. The goal of the mentor in the checkpoint meeting is to *support the mentee's reflection and offer extra material and guidance to prospect a new week of studies* (item b), mainly when the target level of proficiency is not achieved in the current week. It is crucial here that the mentors are experienced Teaching Assistants (TAs), not teachers. We chose to have TAs as mentors for two reasons, namely the shorter *social distance* of students and TAs and to foster community building. First, TAs are more experienced students and, therefore, they understand the needs of 1st-year students, which makes them suitable to help teachers understand and adapt to students' needs. Second, our mentoring system states that a 2nd-year student acts as a Jr. Mentor paired with a 3rd-year student, who acts as a Head Mentor. This helps us foster community building and last-longing commitment with the learning of programming. We select TAs that are both technically skilled and willing to share their expertise with the mentees. However, although they are keen on the activity, they need guidance to mentor. So, the Personal Learning Records offer the basis for starting the conversation with the mentees and focusing on each week's learning goals. This intervention resulted in a new flow for the course, as illustrated in Fig. 2.

Every week, the students have a list of challenges based on the topics taught in the lectures of the current week. These are also the same topics for the self-assessment of the week. The students must submit their exercises to an online grading system, that we configured with special scripts for applying automated tests and automatic grading based on the tests (included, but not limited, to Unit Tests ¹). Once a student has submitted the exercises, the mentors can give inline feedback on any part of the submitted code. The goal is to give support in case the code fails to achieve the threshold of points to get signed-off. The weekly exercises must be submitted by the student and signed-off by the mentor up to the Monday

¹Unit Testing is a software testing technique in which individual units of code are tested to assess if they fit the specification [23]. In Object-Oriented Programming languages, like Java, this unit of code is a class.

Figure 2: The new course flow featuring the bi-weekly checkpoint meetings.

of the following week.

Because the mentors sign-off the exercises, they have a good opportunity to check if the self-assessments done by their mentees are accurate. They are asked to provide the same assessment to each of their mentees, so that the teacher can see the discrepancy between the self-attributed level of proficiency and that attributed by the mentor.

4.1 The Personal Learning Records

The structured self-assessment is done with the support of the Personal Learning Records: an intricate combination of online connected Google Spreadsheets that are shared among the students (≈ 130 students), mentors (13) and teachers (3). The dashboard with the self-assessment and mentor-assessment is illustrated in Fig. 3. The green color indicates that the student self-assessed her proficiency that level. The yellow bar (right below) represents the mentor's assessment of their mentee's proficiency based on the weekly challenges they signed off. The structured syllabus is composed of Learning Objectives that can be learned in approximately one day of study. Each week has approximately 5-6 topics to be learned. This dashboard view of Fig. 3 is visible only to the teachers, who can select other mentors/mentees on the top of the spreadsheet. Mentors have a similar spreadsheet that lists only their mentees, while mentees can only see their own data. In addition, teachers have access to some aggregated data, like a chart showing the proportion of students that self-assessed their proficiency in each topic. This chart makes it visible to the teacher the topics that students had difficulty to learn, allowing for some supportive actions (like Q&A sessions) during the course.

5 RESULTS

We used an ethnographic approach for collecting the data to investigate the research questions presented in Section 2. We observed and collected spontaneous comments and reactions of students and mentors during the course, analyzed reports, essays, and grades. Our first goal is to understand how students perceive the proposed self-assessment model (RQ1). This understanding is critical to avoid a misperception between those proposing the model (teachers) and those playing the roles in the model (students and mentor)². Additionally, we monitor the effects of the interventions with performance indicators that the community considers necessary, as the pass rate in the current and future programming courses and the quality of the projects delivered by the students (RQ2).

The pass rate radically changed from last year to the current. While in 2019-2020 academic

²An adaptation of Michel de Certeau in 'The Practice of Everyday Life' [24] to our context: *what a teacher considers as a support activity may be perceived simply as extra work by the students.*

Personal Learning Records		Mentor	Student	Checkpoint
LO Code	Learning Objective	Entry	Intermediate	Checkpoint 4 Target
P0001	Java Programming Fundamentals	I can describe what is a program and I can state the difference between a process (program) and a thread. I can explain what is the Java Virtual Machine and how it works.	I can develop small programs in Java, even though I may eventually make syntax mistakes.	I can examine a given piece of Java code, break it down into smaller parts and make inferences about the way it works.
P0101	Java Syntax Fundamentals	I am able to list the main syntax' rules. Given a piece of code, I can identify: blocks of code, classes, functions/methods, variable declaration, constants.	I can examine a given code and solve simple syntax errors, like: punctuation, case-sensitiveness related issues, correct opening and closing of curly brackets ({}), etc..	I can develop small programs using correct Java Syntax if I have at least the support of an IDE like Eclipse.
P0102	Variables and Constants in Java	I can explain how to declare and use variables and constants of primitive types in Java (int, double, char, String boolean).	I can explain the specificities of the String type, I know how to properly compare the value of 2 String vars. I can explain and apply the concepts of autoboxing and unboxing.	I can create non-primitive types in Java, i.e., I can develop a class with multiple properties (inner variables).
P0103	Conditionals	I can explain what are and how to use the different conditional structures (IF and Switch) in at least one programming language.	I can explain what is the logic used to build the conditional structure of a given piece of code and differentiate lazy and eager evaluations.	I can develop small pieces of code using conditional structures (IF and Switch) of Java language.
P0104	Blocks and Subroutines	I can explain what is a block of code and I can recognize the different blocks and their hierarchies in a given piece of code.	I can indicate whether or not to create a new subroutine or arrange/re-arrange (refactoring) a code into smaller subroutines using Java language.	I develop subroutines fluently, creating methods for my classes that maximize the reuse of code and improve their maintainability.
P0105	Repetition Structures (loops)	I can explain what are the main repetition structures of Java language (while loop, do-while loop, for-loop) and the syntax of each one.	I can develop small pieces of code in Java (like finding a value in a list), and I can identify which repetition structures best suits the problem at hand.	I can develop more sophisticated loops, like iterating over a collection of objects using optimised for-loop, combine Loops and Generics, etc.
P0106	Exception Handling Fundamentals	I can explain what are Java Exceptions and explain the syntax of a try..catch block on a Java code.	-- intentionally empty --	I can develop Java code to handle Exceptions using try-catch blocks.

Figure 3: Dashboard with learning objectives and friendly rubrics for each level.

year we had a pass rate for the BIT group of 38% (compared to 55% of CS students in the same year), in the 2020-2021 academic year the pass rate of the BIT group almost doubled and reached 68%. We didn't focus exclusively on the pass rate, but on a combination of key performance indicators that include also the quality of their projects and their performance in future programming courses, to understand the long-term effects of developing their Metacognition skills. Therefore, a complete view of their performance must be taken from a longitudinal analysis on the results of the upcoming years. The current result, however, motivates us to continue improving the approach of using Metacognition with mentoring in our courses.

Regarding, student's perceptions, most students were very enthusiastic about the approach. We ran a survey at the end of the course and we had 42 (out of 90) respondents. We asked whether we should keep or remove the self-assessment routine for the next years and 93% (n=42) stated that we should keep it. They perceived the activity as supportive because they were receiving weekly feedback on their assignments and advice on how to improve their proficiency in various topics, for example, to prepare for the exams. We believe the association of the mentoring system with the self-assessment may have had a positive influence in attitude of the students towards the checkpoint meetings, since according to the rules, they could only schedule a checkpoint meeting after updating their Personal Learning Records for the week. Figure 4 illustrates their evaluation of the self-assessment routine.

They recognized the benefits of structuring their reflection in topics and of their checkpoint meetings with the mentor. The following comments from students, answered in the open questions of the survey, illustrate this perception.

I think it is good because it gives structure. You know when you will work on what. It is also easy to discuss with your mentor what you find difficult and what you don't. Then the mentor can also easily share his thoughts about your progress. Without the learning journey I don't think the mentor meeting would go as well. This introduces talking topics. [Student #28]

I liked that it gave me a clear overview of all the topics and the different levels I could study it.

Figure 4: Students had a positive reaction to the self-assessment routine.

It calmed me down to realize that with trying hard for the weekly assignments, I was already on a pretty good level for the test. I definitely advise you to keep it!. [Student #17]

However, not all students saw it the same way. The most disciplined ones and the ones with best performance may have seen this as unnecessary, at least partially. The following comments were provided by students with a high-performance (belonging to the top 5 grades):

For people who have self-discipline I think it does not make a big difference. But for people who need extra motivation I think it is a good idea [Student #02]

I didn't find much use for it as most of the topics were already rather familiar to me and it didn't seem worth it to track of what I already knew. [Student #04]

(...) the truth for Academic Skills part? 'Cause the only think I used the PLR for is getting topics for the exam preparation. [Student #03]

The approach of using structured self-assessment combined with mentoring was indeed designed to support the development of Metacognition skills, mainly in the students with low performance. While we had a partial attendance to the survey, it's quite illustrative that only the students with high performance said the routine didn't seem necessary to them. These are students that did not need much support from mentors and, because of that, some of them skipped the self-assessment and the checkpoint meetings. This may have contributed to their perception of the self-assessment not being useful. Even for these students, the structured syllabus used in the self-assessment helped them organize their studies for the exams. Their reflections bring us the challenge of reviewing the approach to keep these students as engaged as the others, to further develop their Metacognition skills.

6 FINAL REMARKS

In this paper, we presented our approach to support the development of Metacognition skills in students who presented a lower performance in previous years, namely the students of the B-BIT Programme. We analyzed the students' perception of the approach and the pass rate as a first step to assess the effects of our intervention. Students were very optimistic about the approach and the course received the highest grade (since the beginning of the yearly inquiry) in the anonymous course evaluation form, which is ran by the quality assurance team of our university. The pass rate increased dramatically and now is similar to those of the CS students. The enthusiastic feedback sent by the students, both on our surveys and the independent one, and the improved pass rate have motivated us to continue developing the approach.

Regarding our RQ1, we still have no conclusive data regarding the questions *Do students correctly self-assess their level of proficiency? Do they overestimate or underestimate their levels of proficiency? How does it compare to the grades they obtained?.* We did ask them to predict their performance, but we used a qualitative scale and realized later that the multicultural environment brings different meanings of what defines good grades. Given that the course is challenging, for most students a 5.5 grade is a good grade (it is the minimum required to pass the course). However, for other students, the goal is to achieve the maximum grade. We will

solve this in future editions of the course.

Our approach is not specifically designed for teaching computer programming. However, this course is by far the most challenging in which we used this approach and we believe it provided a unique point of view for the effects of a structured reflection. We repeatedly see the different points-of-view students have about the approach, namely the top-performers versus the low-performers. For the latter, this approach helps structure the studies and focus the attention, while the former tends to perceive it as tedious extra work.

Currently, we are collecting data on their Metacognition skills (and the pass rate) in the most advanced programming courses. The goal is to understand the long-term effects of developing their Metacognition skills on their learning performance. Our future work, includes fine-tuning the approach by adding better software support and more frequent self-assessment. Because of the lack of a proper automated system to support the self-assessment, we could only collect and aggregate data every two weeks. To address this, the Personal Learning Records system is currently being developed as a mobile application to be used in the next edition of the course, aiming at allowing students to self-assess at any time.

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